

Antifungal Activity of *Curcuma amada* Roxb. Against *Fusarium oxysporum*

Sawalkar AS¹ and Kadam RM²

¹Research student of Department of Botany, Shivaji College Udgir, MS, India

²Head of the Department of Botany, Mahatma Gandhi College Ahmedpur, MS, India

Affiliated to Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University Nanded, MS, India

*Corresponding author Email: rmk76@rediffmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this study was to determine, in vitro, the antifungal activity of *Curcuma amada* Roxb. ethanolic rhizome extract against the seed-borne fungal pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum*. The food poisoning method was used to test the extract at 2.5%, 5%, and 10% concentrations. The negative control was 0.5% ethanol, and the positive control was a commercial fungicide (Valxtra). The findings demonstrated a dose-dependent, substantial decrease in mycelial growth. The 10% concentration showed the highest inhibition (71.74%), which was similar to the fungicide treatment (78.26%). One-way ANOVA statistical analysis showed substantial changes between treatments ($p < 0.001$). With an Rf value of 0.75, HPTLC analysis verified the presence of curcumin. The results indicate that *C. amada* rhizome extract possesses strong antifungal potential and may serve as an eco-friendly biofungicide for sustainable crop protection. The present investigation was conducted to evaluate the antifungal activity of ethanolic rhizome extract

Keywords: *Curcuma amada*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, antifungal activity, food poison technique, curcumin, biofungicide

INTRODUCTION

Seed-borne fungal pathogens are responsible for seed deterioration, reduced germination, and yield losses in agricultural crops. Fungi such as *Aspergillus spp.* and *Fusarium spp.* are commonly associated with seeds and stored grains (Agarwal & Sinclair, 1997). are responsible for significant economic losses. Among them, *Fusarium oxysporum* is an important pathogen causing vascular wilt and seed infection in many crops. Chemical fungicides are widely used for management; however, their continuous application has resulted in environmental pollution and resistance development (Brent & Hollomon, 2007). Medicinal plants are considered rich sources of bioactive secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds with antimicrobial properties (Cowan, 1999). Although synthetic fungicides are widely used for disease management, their excessive and continuous application has resulted in environmental pollution, health hazards, and the

development of resistant fungal strains. Therefore, there is increasing interest in exploring plant-derived natural products as safer and sustainable alternatives. Mango ginger (*Curcuma amada*) is a remarkable perennial herbaceous plant whose rhizomes have a physical similarity to ginger but have a distinct mango flavour. Mango ginger is a popular item in India. Rhizomes are golden brown in colour, bear certain layers, and are used in food. *C. amada* belongs to the Zingiberaceae family. *C. amada* has a huge amount of potential as a medicinal herb, colourant, and flavouring. In addition to being used in the making of pickles, *C. amada* is also used as a source of raw mango flavour in meals and as a medicinal herb. The rhizome is important in Ayurveda, Plants have been found to create a number of chemicals to defend themselves against a wide range of infections, and as a result, they are regarded as being a possible source for a range of antimicrobial agents of various types. As a result, the present investigation was performed in order to determine the antibacterial activity of *C. amada* rhizome extracts. *C. amada* has long been valued for its therapeutic potential. Antifungal and antibacterial activity of *C. amada* has been observed in some investigations *Curcuma amada* Roxb., belonging to the family Zingiberaceae, is traditionally used in Ayurveda for its medicinal value. It contains curcuminoids and essential oils responsible for antimicrobial and antioxidant activities (Policegoudra et al., 2007). Curcumin, a major bioactive constituent, has been reported to exhibit antifungal activity by disrupting fungal cell membranes (Martins et al., 2009). Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the antifungal activity of *C. amada* rhizome extract against seed-borne fungal pathogens.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Isolation of Fungi from diseased specimen

Different strains of fungi were isolated from selected seeds from some crop and vegetable crops were collected from local market shops and from farmers of Osmanabad and Beed district, Axenic culture of the pathogen was obtained by single hyphal tip method and maintained in PDA slants by periodical sub-culturing and used for further studies.

2.2 Collection and Preparation of Plant Material

Plant extraction was performed in accordance with (Abdulaziz et al. 2013), with modest modifications.

2.2 Collection and Preparation of Plant Extract

Dried rhizomes of *Curcuma amada* were procured from a local Ayurvedic medicinal shop in Ambajogai, Maharashtra. The rhizomes were washed thoroughly, shade-dried, and powdered using a mechanical grinder. 30 grams of powdered rhizome was macerated in 150 mL of 95% ethanol (1:5 w/v) for 72 hours at room temperature with occasional shaking. The extract was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentrated on a water bath to obtain a thick crude extract. The extract was stored at 5°C until use.

2.3 Phytochemical analysis by HPTLC

Curcumin in *Curcuma amada* was analyzed by thin layer chromatography (TLC). Dried rhizome powder (1 g) was extracted with 10 mL of methanol by overnight shaking at room temperature. The extract was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and used for chromatographic analysis. A standard stock solution of curcumin was prepared in methanol, and the working standard solution was obtained by diluting 100 µL of the stock solution with 400 µL of methanol. Appropriate volumes of standard and sample solutions were applied as bands on pre-coated silica gel aluminium TLC plates 60 F254 (20 × 10 cm, 250 µm thickness; Merck) using a Camag Linomat 5 applicator fitted with a 100 µL Hamilton micro syringe. Linear ascending development was carried out in a twin-trough chamber (20 × 10 cm) previously saturated with the mobile phase chloroform: methanol (9.5:0.5, v/v). After development, plates were air-dried and observed under UV light at 254 nm and 366 nm. The chromatograms were documented photographically to assess band resolution. Densitometric scanning was performed using a Camag TLC Scanner 3 operated in reflectance-absorbance mode and controlled by WINCATS software, employing deuterium and tungsten lamps as radiation sources.

2.4 Test Pathogens

Seed-borne fungal pathogens *Fusarium oxysporum* were isolated from infected seeds and purified on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium.

2.5 Food Poison Technique

Antifungal activity of leaf extracts:

The antifungal efficacy of leaf extracts was determined by the poisoned food technique. PDA media amended with different concentrations of leaf extracts (2.5, 5 and 10 %) were sterilised by autoclaving and added to labelled Petri dishes. The control plate, untreated

control, 0.5% ethanol and 0.5% valxtra in the medium was used. The fungal mycelial growth in untreated and 0.5% ethanol was the same; there was no significant difference. Hence, 0.5% ethanol and 0.5% valxtra were used as a control for comparison. The medium was poured into 90 mm Petri plates at 15 ml/plate. The fungal discs of 5 mm size obtained from seven days old culture were inoculated at the centre of the Petri plates and incubated at room temperature (28 ± 2 °C) for 7 days. Three replications were maintained for each treatment, and a control plate was also maintained. The diameter of the mycelial growth (cm) of pathogens was measured and recorded after 7 days of incubation. Antifungal activity was recorded in terms of inhibition of mycelial growth (%) and calculated using the formula.

2.6 Inhibition of mycelial growth (%) = $(C - T/C) \cdot 100$

where 'C' is the average diameter of the fungal colony in control plates and 'T' is the average diameter of the fungal colony in poisoned plates (Gupta and Tripathi, 2011). To observe the significant differences between the percentage mycelial growth inhibition of the plant extracts and the control against the isolated pathogen, one-way and two-way ANOVA were used, respectively. SPSS software was used to calculate all statistical analyses. (J Anal Tech Res 2019; 1(1): 047-063. DOI: 10.26502.)

RESULTS

Phytochemical analysis by HPTLC

The effect of rhizome extracts *Curcuma amada* in reducing mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* was summarized in Table 1. Plates of *Fusarium oxysporum*, Maximum inhibition of mycelial growth (1.3 cm.) was obtained with 10.0% concentration, which accounted for 71.74 % reduction over control. This was followed by 2.5% and 5.0% extract with 3.4 cm. and 2.00 cm. with 26.09% and 56.52 % reduction over the control, respectively. At 2.5% concentration showed least inhibition (3.4 cm.) with 26.09%, and the negative control plate (ethanol) recorded an average 4.6 cm. and positive control (valxtra) recorded (1.00 cm) mycelial growth after seven days.

The values of F indicated that there was significant variation due to various concentrations of *Curcuma amada* extract, while the variation due to the replication was statistically non-significant. The

mycelial growth significantly and gradually decreased from 4.6 cm. in control to 1.3 cm. at the concentration of 10.0 %.

HPTLC plate under visible light

HPTLC plate at 254 nm

HPTLC plate observed at 366 nm

Track 1: Blank (Methanol; 2 μ L)
Track 2: Curcumin Standard (2000 ng/band)
Track 3: *Curcuma amada* extract (10 μ L)
Track 4: Blank (Methanol; 2 μ L)

Photoplate 1: Medicinal Plant Used for Phytochemical analysis by HPTLC

The ethanolic rhizome extract of *Curcuma amada* exhibited significant antifungal activity against the tested *Fusarium oxysporum* fungal pathogens. The inhibition percentage increased progressively from 2.5% to 10% concentration, demonstrating a dose-dependent response. Maximum inhibition was observed at 10% concentration and was comparable to the standard fungicide treatment. ANOVA results indicated significant differences among treatments, confirming the efficacy of the plant extract. ANOVA analysis revealed highly significant differences among treatments ($F = 686.400$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the extract concentration significantly affected fungal growth. Replication differences were statistically non-significant. The results clearly demonstrate a dose-dependent antifungal effect. HPTLC analysis confirmed the presence of curcumin ($R_f = 0.75$), indicating that curcuminoids may be responsible for the observed antifungal activity.

0.5% ethanol (control plate) 0.5% valxtra (control plate)

2.5% conc. 5% conc. 10% conc

Photoplate 2: Antifungal activity of *Curcuma amada* on *Fusarium oxysporum*:

Figure 1: Densitogram of all tracks (Scanned @ 425 nm) of *Curcuma amada*

Figure 2: Spectra Comparison of Peak at Rf - 0.75 (Standard and Sample *Curcuma amada*)

- Curcuminoids present in Sample . Ambehalad (*Curcuma amada*)
- HPTLC analysis confirmed the presence of curcumin (Rf = 0.75)

Table 1. Effect of *Curcuma amada* on percentage growth inhibition of *Fusarium oxysporum*:

Sr no.	Extract concentration%	Linear mycelial growth in cm				Growth inhibition %
		R1	R2	R3	Mean	
1	Control	4.6	4.7	4.5	4.60 ± 0.06	0.00
2	2.5	3.4	3.5	3.3	3.40 ± 0.06	26.09
3	5	2	2.1	1.9	2.00 ± 0.06	56.52
4	10	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.30 ± 0.06	71.74
5	Valxtra (+ve control)	1	1.1	0.9	1.00 ± 0.06	78.26

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	27.456	4	6.864	686.400	0.000
Within Groups	0.100	10	0.010		
Total	27.556	14			
CD _{5%}	0.182				
CD _{1%}	0.259				

Figure 4. Effect of *Curcuma amada* extract on the growth inhibition percentage and linear mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum*.

The study confirms that *Curcuma amada* rhizome extract possesses significant antifungal activity against seed-borne fungal pathogens. The presence of curcumin (Rf 0.75) supports its bioactive potential. The extract may serve as a promising eco-friendly alternative to chemical fungicides in crop disease management.

DISCUSSION

The antifungal activity observed in the present study may be attributed to curcumin and other phenolic compounds present in *Curcuma amada*. Curcumin has been reported to inhibit fungal growth by altering membrane permeability and interfering with enzymatic activity (Martins et al., 2009). The dose-dependent inhibition pattern supports earlier findings on plant-derived antifungal compounds (Cowan, 1999). *Curcuma amada* displayed significant efficacy against the majority of the tested microorganisms. The findings were similar to the antibiotics used as a control group. The findings of this research provide considerable proof that *C. amada* rhizome is a potent antibacterial agent. Extracts of *C. amada* rhizome were shown to be efficacious against all organisms tested, including antibacterial strains, fungal strains, which were receptive to all extracts of *C. amada* rhizome. The findings show that *C. amada* extracts in petroleum ether, DCM, and chloroform have considerable antibacterial and antifungal power. (Nand Kumar Kashyap, Jeetendra Deepak et. al. 2022) Plant extracts provide eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic fungicides and reduce environmental hazards (Brent & Hollomon, 2007). Therefore, *C. amada* rhizome extract shows potential as a natural bio fungicide for sustainable agriculture.

CONCLUSION

The study confirms that *Curcuma amada* rhizome extract possesses significant antifungal activity against seed-borne fungal pathogens. The presence of curcumin (Rf 0.75) supports its bioactive potential. The extract may serve as a promising eco-friendly alternative to chemical fungicides in crop disease management.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to **Sawalkar AS**

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